

Open and Programmable Accelerators for Data-intensive Applications in the Cloud

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Physical and System-Level Deployment Model	7
3. Logical Accelerator-Enhanced Cloud Stack	9
4. Support for the Three Demonstrators	10
5. Conclusions	11
Bibliography	12

List of Figures

Figure 1: Server components in an accelerator-based cloud environment.....	8
Figure 2: Logical software stack in an accelerator-based cloud environment.	9

List of Abbreviations

SSD Solid-State Drive

NIC Network Interface Card

OCP Open Compute Project

Executive Summary

This document defines the relevant environment in which our programmable accelerators (OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V) as well as the data-intensive patterns library will be demonstrated with three use cases: a data lake system, a machine learning inference pipeline, and CYSO object store. The environment is based on real hardware and is explicitly designed to emulate and capture the essential architectural and dataflow properties of production cloud systems, showing that such systems can be built around programmable storage and network accelerators.

The environment is anchored in standard rack-server deployments augmented with programmable SSDs and NICs, and in a software organization in which access to the accelerators is provided through dedicated management and programming interfaces that do not disrupt the natural structure of cloud software stacks. These interfaces allow both system software and applications to configure, control, and invoke accelerator functionality using abstractions compatible with existing cloud practices.

Taken together, this demonstration setup intends to validate that programmable storage and network devices can be integrated as first-class cloud resources, support distinct classes of data-intensive workloads, and provide a credible foundation for adoption in future cloud platforms.

1 Introduction

This document defines the accelerator-based cloud environment that will be used to implement and showcase the three CHORYS demonstrators based on the OpenSSD-V and OpenNIC-V at TRL 6. The goal is not to replicate or reimplement a full hyperscale cloud infrastructure, but rather to specify a minimal yet realistic environment that is sufficient to convincingly demonstrate how cloud applications can be built around programmable storage and network accelerators. The environment is designed so that a cloud provider can directly map its components and abstractions onto existing production stacks.

The environment targets three representative application classes (described in Deliverable 2.2 [3]) : an object store enhanced with near-storage caching and processing, a data lake system that offloads parsing and query operators to storage and network devices, and a machine learning workflow in which our accelerators support high-throughput, low-latency data movement between storage and GPU-based inference nodes. We rely on the architecture defined in Deliverable 2.4 [2] to ensure that all three demonstrators operate within the same architectural framework, rather than relying on use-case-specific platforms.

From a validation perspective, the environment is defined to support the following objectives: (i) demonstrate that OpenSSD-V and OpenNIC-V can be deployed as first-class cloud devices within standard rack servers; (ii) show that cloud application stacks can invoke accelerator functionality through well-defined software layers and APIs, without requiring application redesign around device-specific interfaces; and (iii) enable meaningful performance and functional evaluations for near-storage processing, in-network processing, and accelerator-assisted GPU workflows under realistic dataflow conditions.

Accordingly, the remainder of this document specifies: in Section 2, the physical and system-level deployment model assumed for rack-scale servers equipped with OpenSSD-V and OpenNIC-V; in Section 3, the logical structure of the accelerator-enhanced software stack, including runtime, programming, and management interfaces; and in Section 4, the way in which this common environment supports the three demonstrators.

2 Physical and System-Level Deployment Model

The accelerator-based environment presented in this document follows the architecture described in Deliverable D2.2 [3]. It is centered on standard rack-mounted cloud servers augmented with OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V devices. The intent is to remain fully compatible with current data center design practices, while selectively replacing or extending conventional network and storage devices with their accelerated counterparts. No specialized chassis, interconnects, or non-standard host components are assumed. Put differently, this model is consistent with the Open Compute Project (OCP) rack and tray specifications defined by the server project ¹.

Each server is composed of conventional host components, as illustrated in Figure 1. These components include multi-core CPUs, main memory, optional GPUs for compute-intensive workloads (designed as INF for inference and TRN for training in the figure), PCIe interconnects, and a mix of solid-state storage and network interfaces. Within this baseline configuration, OpenNIC-V replaces or complements a traditional Network Interface Card (NIC), and

¹<https://www.opencompute.org/projects/server>

Figure 1: Server components in an accelerator-based cloud environment.

OpenSSD-V replaces or complements a traditional NVMe Solid-State Drive (SSD). Both devices are attached via PCIe and participate in the same I/O and memory hierarchy as their non-accelerated counterparts. Task 9.2 focuses on the system integration of such a server, based on a Rhea processor.

From a dataflow perspective, OpenNIC-V sits directly on the network ingress and egress path, enabling packet- and stream-level processing before data reaches host memory or GPUs. The initial design of OpenNIC-V is described in deliverable D6.1 [1]. OpenSSD-V sits directly on the persistent storage path, enabling near-storage processing during read and write operations. The host CPU remains responsible for control-plane logic, orchestration, and application-level coordination, while OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V execute selected data-plane operations using their integrated RISC-V cores and specialized accelerators.

This deployment model supports several important system-level properties that are required by all three demonstrators. First, accelerators are positioned on the critical data paths for network and storage, enabling meaningful evaluation of near-data and in-network processing. Second, host-side execution remains unchanged at the hardware level, preserving compatibility with existing cloud software stacks and GPU-based workloads. Third, multiple accelerators can coexist within the same server, allowing combined OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V configurations to support end-to-end accelerated data pipelines.

At the rack level, the environment naturally scales by populating multiple such servers under a conventional top-of-rack switching infrastructure. An independent storage chassis might be used to group multiple OpenSSD-V SSDs within a rack ², and OpenNIC-V might be located in hot swappable modules dedicated to NICs as envisaged by OCP. Adhering to the standard rack setup ensures that the demonstrators remain representative of how a cloud provider could incrementally introduce OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V into existing clusters without disruptive architectural changes.

²<https://www.opencompute.org/projects/storage>

Figure 2: Logical software stack in an accelerator-based cloud environment.

3 Logical Accelerator-Enhanced Cloud Stack

The logical structure of the accelerator-enhanced cloud environment is defined as a software stack that spans from the OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V hardware up to the demonstrator software layers. The purpose of this structure is twofold: to isolate device-specific details behind stable runtime and programming interfaces, and to emulate the essential structure of a full cloud stack without requiring the construction of a complete production-grade cloud infrastructure.

At the lowest level, the devices execute programs on their integrated RISC-V cores and specialized hardware accelerators, operating directly on network and storage data streams. Above this, a device-side runtime and driver layer provides the basic execution environment for accelerator programs, including program loading, I/O coordination, memory management, and interaction with host software. This layer is responsible for exposing the accelerators as programmable cloud resources rather than fixed-function devices.

On top of the runtime, two main API classes are provided. The programming APIs allow developers to target the RISC-V cores and accelerators using software abstractions suitable for dataflow-oriented computations such as filtering, parsing, aggregation, and data structure transformation. The management APIs expose device configuration, monitoring, and isolation mechanisms to the host-side control plane, enabling integration with cloud orchestration, scheduling, and accounting mechanisms. Together, these APIs define the boundary between

the accelerator subsystem and the host cloud software environment.

The upper part of the stack consists of host-side system software and demonstrator runtimes that emulate central aspects of an object store, a data lake system, and a machine learning data pipeline. These stacks are not intended to be full reimplementations of production systems. Instead, they are designed to reproduce the key data paths, control interactions, and performance-critical behaviors required to convincingly demonstrate how such systems could benefit from OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V by adopting the provided runtimes and APIs. All interactions with the accelerators occur exclusively through these interfaces, in the same way that cloud services interact with conventional programmable devices.

This layered organization establishes a common logical environment for all three demonstrators. It allows OpenNIC-V and OpenSSD-V to appear as programmable, manageable cloud devices, while preserving a clean separation between application logic, system software, and hardware execution.

4 Support for the Three Demonstrators

The accelerator-based environment defined in the preceding sections is designed to support all three demonstrators within a single, common architectural framework, rather than relying on use-case-specific platforms. Each demonstrator exercises a different class of data-intensive cloud workload, but all rely on the same physical deployment model and the same logical accelerator-enhanced stack. In the remaining of this section, we describe the environment in which the use cases are demonstrated as we envisage it today.

In the object store demonstrator, OpenSSD-V is used to support a near-storage cache and a near-storage processing layer. The demonstrator emulates the core data path of an object storage service in which read and write requests traverse a storage stack before reaching applications. Selected operations such as filtering, metadata extraction, and cache population are offloaded to the OpenSSD-V runtime through the programming APIs. The objective is to demonstrate how object-level services can transparently exploit near-storage processing without restructuring application logic around device-specific interfaces.

In the machine learning demonstrator, OpenSSD-V is used as a paging and swapping device for GPU memory in an inference-oriented setting. The demonstrator targets scenarios in which large models exceed the effective capacity of GPU memory and where substantial portions of the model weights are accessed only briefly during inference. OpenSSD-V supports rapid staging of model parameters between persistent storage and GPU-accessible memory, with selected data movement and transformation operations offloaded to the near-storage execution environment. This allows the demonstrator to emulate memory pressure and data orchestration effects that arise in large-scale inference services, without modifying the inference framework itself.

In the data lake demonstrator, OpenSSD-V and OpenNIC-V jointly support accelerated parsing and query-oriented data manipulation. The demonstrator emulates a SQL-over-files access pattern in which large analytical datasets are read from storage, parsed, and filtered before being consumed by higher-level query operators. Parsing, projection, and predicate evaluation are mapped to accelerator programs through the same programming and runtime layers defined in Section 3. This shows how the environment supports query pushdown across storage and network paths while preserving the structure of a conventional data lake stack.

Across all three demonstrators, the key property is that accelerator functionality is accessed

exclusively through the common runtime, programming, and management interfaces described in Section 3. This ensures that the demonstrators validate not only individual acceleration techniques, but the viability of the overall environment as a reusable foundation for different classes of cloud applications.

5 Conclusions

This document has defined a relevant accelerator-based cloud environment for the OpenSSD-V and OpenNIC-V platforms, with the specific goal of enabling realistic and convincing demonstrators without requiring the construction of a full cloud infrastructure. By grounding the environment in standard rack-server deployments and by defining a common logical accelerator-enhanced software stack, the document establishes a setting that cloud providers can directly relate to existing production systems.

Within this environment, the three demonstrators—object store, data lake, and machine learning inference—exercise complementary data-intensive workloads while relying on the same architectural foundations. Together, they validate the feasibility of integrating programmable storage and network accelerators into cloud application stacks and illustrate concrete paths by which such accelerators could be adopted in practice.

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